

Supplementary Figure 5: NKG2A-edited primary NK and NK-92 cells act synergistically with RIG-I stimulation to promote anti-tumor toxicity.

(a) Surface expression of NKG2A and HLA-E on the surface of NK cells or target cells alone was measured by flow cytometry on control wells from experiments in Fig. 5a, and Sup. Fig. 5b. (b) Cytotoxicity of the NKG2A-edited primary NK cells in combination with RIG-I stimulation in the target cells A-431 (mean and SD from n=4 donors) and Capan-2 (mean and SD from n=5 donors), as indicated in Fig. 5. (c) Contribution to total NK cytotoxicity of RIG-I stimulation in the target cells A-431 and Capan-2, and the combination of both was calculated for E:T ratio 2.5:1, as indicated in Fig. 5. (d-f) Cocultures of RIG-I stimulated target cells and NKG2A-edited NK-92 cells. Target cells were stimulated 24 h before cocultures with 0.4 μ g/ml RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA), and NKG2A and HLA-E expression were measured in control wells where only NK-92 or target cells were present (d), specific lysis was measured by flow cytometry against A-431, Capan-2, and A549 (e, Mean \pm SD specific lysis from at least 3 independent experiments at different E:T ratios are shown), and contributions to total NK cytotoxicity was calculated for the E:T ratio 2.5:1 (f). Statistical comparisons were performed using paired t test for surface expression of HLA-E and NKG2A (a, d) or two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šídák's post-hoc test (b, e). *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.